

8T –Manifold Jumps and Pharrell Transport

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T, under the emphasis over topologically invariant manifolds, it than becomes vivid that it is possible to switch from manifold to another manifold, that is given by the Same Ricci flow on each manifold. The 8T framework allows jumps from manifold to manifold, given by the fact that those manifolds are interacting in areas of extremum curvatures.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor M , given by the conditions on (1.1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant, i.e. they have the same distribution of extremum curvatures.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The implicit assumption of equation of (1.2) is that in order of the universe packet to flatten each other the curvatures on the manifolds must be interfacing. That is synonymous with stating that the universe packet must have topologically invariant manifolds, or manifolds in which the extremum curvature distribution is identical on the metric tensor. That is because in the manifolds flatten each other due to the interaction of those areas, if they are not interacting the flattening, i.e. dark energy would not be correct. It is possible to prove that if there were only two manifolds, which are not interacting with each other via those areas, equation (1.2) will not be correct; the universe would not be flat as we measure it today. The requirement of the universe packet than imposes a symmetry in a sense that only topologically invariant manifolds are "allowed" on the packet. We do not know whether it is actually the case but so it seems by equation (1.2) and the "thought experiment" of only two manifolds interacting in the packet, assumed different topology. Another point to mention is same topology does mean same matter distribution on each manifold. Distinct manifold can have a dust of gas of certain curvature, which is equivalent to the mass of a certain galaxy on another manifold. Those universes differ from each other in a distance measure which is not known, can could vary as other topologically invariant manifolds enter the packet. Between each manifold pair there is the same base space, Ricci flow, given by the fourth term of (1.2). everything written up to this point was already covered in 8T previous papers. From here we have a completely new paper.

Since the manifolds have the same curvature distribution, they have the same energy given by the term of the Ricci flow, if you can switch from the metric tensor of one manifold to its flow, and the flow is the same for all the manifolds in the packet, than you can jump or get into the metric tensor of another manifold. In other words, the Ricci flow is the kernel of the entire manifold packet. That is by equation (1.2) and the fact that each manifold, which flatten each other interact by the areas of extremum curvatures $\partial g/\partial t = 0$. So to switch from manifold to manifold, it will require an immense amount of energy, and such an energy level would lead to a deformation of the metric tensor to the kernel, the Ricci flow, and from the Ricci flow we can reach again the metric tensor of a distinct manifold. 8T than regard the metric tensor of each manifold to be a map to another metric tensor. below are two illustrations, the first is the universe packet, the metric is the dark part and the flow is the white part between each two manifolds. the second illustration is an interaction of areas of extremum curvatures between two distinct manifolds, between each two there is the Ricci flow, which is the same for both. The jump from manifold to manifold can be done via this base space.

$$\Leftrightarrow: M_1 \rightarrow M_N \quad (1.3)$$

Another point to emphasize is same topology or curvature distribution does mean identical matter distribution on each manifold. Distinct manifold can have a dust of gas of certain curvature, which is equivalent to the mass of a certain galaxy on another manifold. Those universes differ from each other in a distance measure, which is not known. As the illustration above suggest, they are very close. The packet could vary as other topologically invariant manifolds enter the packet, also known as cosmological singularity. The main point of this short essay between each manifold pair, and actually all the manifolds in the packet is the same base space, Ricci flow, given by the fourth term of (1.2), which allows the jumps, as presented in equation (1.3). Its currently unclear whether there are infinite manifold packets or just one manifold packet which is infinite. It is also unclear whether the question of distance is applicable in the base space, The Ricci flow, as it pure energy oriented.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)